

**Peer Reviewed*

A game-theoretic approach to promoting green buildings among facilities managers *Lydia Tshibe Raphudufudu*¹; *Thulasizwe Percival Abednigo Hadebe*¹ *Ryan Mapfumo*¹ *Yewande Adewunmi*¹ and *Prisca Simbanegavi*¹

¹School of Construction Economics and Management, University of the Witwatersrand,
Email: yewande.adewunmi@wits.ac.za

Abstract

Facilities managers in South Africa are constrained by a lack of awareness and incentives, and may be hesitant to adopt green building practices. The study explored the game-theoretic approach towards the adoption of green building in facilities management in Johannesburg, South Africa. It specifically investigated the adoption of game theory strategies, application areas and game theory incentives towards promoting green buildings by facilities managers. In the context of green building adoption, understanding the behaviours of facility managers is helpful, as it aids in designing effective incentives for environmentally friendly practices. An online survey was sent to a convenience sample of facilities managers managing green buildings in Johannesburg, South Africa, to explore the possible game theory strategies between facilities managers and other stakeholders in the industry, as well as game theory incentives. The results were analysed using descriptive statistics, including mean scores, standard deviation, and correlation analysis. The study found that cooperative games, repeated games, evolutionary game theory, and Nash equilibrium were preferred game strategies. Cost-benefit analysis, resource allocation, regulatory compliance, incentive structuring, and strategic collaboration were sometimes game theory application areas. Non-financial incentives were rated as better than financial incentives for green building adoption. Facilities managers' limited knowledge of game theory can be overcome through joint efforts between researchers and educational institutions.

Keywords: Facilities management; Game theory; Green building adoption; Game theory strategies; incentives.

Introduction

Not many governments have focused on green buildings; however, progress remains slow due to various barriers, including resistance to new technologies, high costs of green materials, insufficient customer demand, and a lack of collaboration among construction stakeholders (Gluch et al., 2013). Research indicates that social and psychological factors hinder the transition to sustainable building practices more than technical challenges. Understanding stakeholder behaviour is crucial for the success of green building policies (Li, 2022).

Game theory is one method that can be used to understand how various stakeholders in the construction industry will act when deciding to produce environmentally friendly structures. Implementing environmentally friendly building practices creates a complex network of strategic interactions among various stakeholders, including users and facility managers. Game theory can help analyse the strategic interactions among stakeholders, providing insights into effective incentives for sustainable construction (Chauhan et al., 2022). Game theory, grounded in mathematical models of strategic interactions among rational decision-makers, provides a comprehensive framework for analysing and shaping decision-making processes in facilities management (Fudenberg and Tirole, 1991). Providing a mathematical framework often used in economics and political science, game theory offers a method for analysing situations of this kind (Myerson, 2013). This study provides valuable insights into the possible interactions that facilities

managers have with stakeholders in green building adoption, including building owners, contractors, and policymakers identified by facilities managers (Bekius and Gomes, 2023).

Game theory can be employed in facilities management to model the strategic interactions among various stakeholders. Player A, a facilities manager, must decide whether to invest in a green building upgrade. This decision affects the manager regarding investment costs and potential future savings while also influencing Player B, the building owner, who may see an increase in property value or incur specific costs (Cohen, Pearlmutter, and Schwarts, 2019). Using game theory to model these interactions allows for the prediction of potential outcomes and the identification of optimal strategies for all participants. This is especially beneficial for developing incentives that promote the adoption of green building practices. A game-theoretic model can illustrate how various financial and regulatory incentives influence facilities managers and other stakeholders (Qingfeng et al., 2021). It also can provide valuable insights into resolving conflicts and planning cooperative frameworks (Shahmohammadian and Ghafory-Ashtiany, 2025).

Locating specific case studies or examples of direct applications of game theory in facilities management presents a challenge. The available information is insufficient, necessitating extrapolation from the overarching principles of game theory and its applications in related domains, such as economics, politics, or the social sciences (Kapliński and Tamošaitienė, 2010). A game-theoretic model can be developed in facilities management involving the Facilities Manager (Player A) and Building Users (Player B). The choice to invest in a green building upgrade is primarily the responsibility of the Facilities Manager regarding operational efficiency. It also impacts the Property Manager, who focuses on the financial performance and marketability of the property (Saka et al., 2021; Alfalah and Zayed, 2020).

Facilities Management (FM) is vital in promoting environmentally friendly building practices. FM can contribute by conducting risk assessments, designing sustainable materials, and planning for future changes in the built environment. However, the lack of incentives is a significant barrier to sustainable development (Li Ang and Wilkinson, 2008). Incentives can be categorised into structural (non-monetary) and financial (monetary), with structural incentives being more feasible for financially constrained entities (Gundes, 2019). Government initiatives, such as the Green Building Policy introduced in 2018, aim to lead in sustainable building by managing resources efficiently and promoting awareness (Department of Public Works).

The construction industry is a major source of global carbon emissions. Green Buildings (GBs) have recently been recognised as a potential solution to this environmental challenge. However, their adoption has been slow due to cost, knowledge gaps, and perceived complexities. Despite advancements in green building research and implementation in South Africa, integration into academia remains limited. Existing regulations focus on waste management, resource efficiency, and environmentally friendly materials (Agbajor and Mewomo, 2024).

Because game theory relies on oversimplified assumptions about self-interested, rational actors, it may not adequately portray the complexity of human behaviour in actual building scenarios, which is why its use in this field is restricted (Shahmohammadian and Ghafory-Ashtiany, 2025). Despite this limitation game theory is still useful for this study. Facilities managers in South Africa are constrained by a lack of awareness and incentives, and may be hesitant to adopt green building practices (Mompoti et al., 2025). Few studies in FM have applied game theory, particularly using

multiple techniques for green building adoption. The study aimed to explore a game-theoretic approach towards promoting green buildings by facilities managers. This study will specifically investigate how FM can use game theory strategies, application areas and incentives that South African facilities managers use to encourage the adoption of sustainable building practices, ultimately promoting a greener future. In the context of green building adoption, understanding the behaviours of facilities managers and stakeholders is helpful, as it aids in designing effective incentives for environmentally friendly practices

Literature Review

Game-Theoretic Strategies

Game-theoretic strategies can provide insights into decision-making dynamics, cooperation, competition, and strategic behaviour among stakeholders, aiding facilities managers in effectively promoting green building practices. Figure 1 shows the game theory strategies identified from the literature review.

Additional Strategies by facilities managers can also foster green building practices by creating incentives, altering local codes, standards, and permitting processes, and considering the building's carbon footprint throughout all planning and design stages (Armbruster and Boge, 1979).

Figure 1: Game theory strategies
Sources: Authors construct (2023)

The Significance of Incentives in Game Theory Models

Incentives are crucial in game theory models, significantly influencing the strategies chosen by players (Gundes and Yildirim, 2015). For example, financial incentives such as tax breaks can motivate facility managers to adopt green construction practices, while social incentives can enhance users satisfaction and improve a company's image (Gundes and Yildirim, 2015). Understanding these influences is crucial for promoting green building practices, particularly when stakeholders can coordinate their strategies (Gundes and Yildirim, 2015).

Financial incentives, including government grants, tax incentives, sustainable development fee refunds and sustainable project loan funds, help mitigate the initial costs of green building technologies, making them more attractive to developers (Simpeh and Smallwood, 2024). Regulatory incentives, such as density bonuses, expedited permit processes and preferential zoning, streamline the development of green projects (Simpeh and Smallwood, 2024). Recognition programs and certifications, such as awards, training, and energy efficiency programs, validate sustainability efforts and provide public acknowledgement (Matisoff et al., 2014; Simpeh and Smallwood, 2024). Other incentives, including free marketing and technical assistance and infrastructure compatibility improvement, address specific challenges in adopting green practices (Simpeh and Smallwood, 2024).

In South Africa, developing eco-friendly structures generally requires more resources, particularly financial, than non-eco-friendly structures. Incentives for green building are essential for promoting sustainable construction practices, particularly if significant compliance with established green building policies is anticipated (Agbajor and Mewomo, 2024). The GBCSA in South Africa supports green construction practices, offering rebates in housing stock and property rates that meet its rating system. The Department of Energy and the South African National Energy Development Institutes establish an income tax allowance for energy efficiency savings. The International Finance Cooperation issued a \$42 million loan package to a non-banking financing company to support small and medium enterprises' housing projects. However, the demand for net zero and positive energy building retrofits remains high, necessitating the development of realistic financial models for sustainable building achievement (Agbajor and Mewomo, 2024).

Game theory studies in facilities management.

In Sweden, Eriksson (2007) empirically utilised the prisoner's dilemma (PD) game to test whether game theory can explain buyer-supplier non-cooperation in construction and facilities management. The payoffs include investments, better communication, and profits from mutual cooperation. He said that a lack of long-term contracts may explain the inconsistent attitude of parties in the Swedish construction industry and that actors should aim to reduce the pay-off disparity to enhance cooperation. In Norway, Hopland (2015) used a game-theoretical approach using a Goodspeed model to examine regional governments' maintenance backlogs and goals. According to the research, regional governments may rationally handle maintenance backlogs if they anticipate the central government to “bail out” them with an additional grant for facility upgrades. Gauteplass and Hopland (2017) also examined how the central government may utilise game-theoretical principles to encourage local public facility supply via asymmetric information. Thus, the central government

would want to stimulate local public facilities by offering local governments a transfer to boost their supply. Tamošaitienė et al. (2013) used game theory to choose commercial estate service providers in Lithuania. Savage rule and Levi 3.0 were used for computations. The case study demonstrated real problem-solving utilising the model. Briata and Fragnelli (2020) in Italy examined the inefficiencies and free-riding that might result from sharing a facility's maintenance cost with possible users and splitting the cost of a check among agents who requested it. They proposed two ways to reduce free-riding and explored the possibility that the check indicates each agent's facility utilisation. The check became more profitable by using a TU-cost game to calculate each agent's total cost quota to please as many agents as feasible. Two options were examined, and the TU-cost game's balance was defined. In the Netherlands, Krogmann et al. (2021) created a model for non-cooperative facility locations where facilities and customers behave strategically and significantly influence one another in the Netherlands. Not all competitive facility placement models with strategic customers are practical, like the load-balancing two-sided facility location game.

Xu et al. (2017) researched multiobjective control in a facility setting in China and solved it using DMPC. A cooperative game theory-based weight allocation and Nash bargaining solution improved facility environment control performance. The simulation studies compared the suggested system to single objective control and linear weighted control to assess its practicality and efficiency. The cooperative game theory-based multiobjective DMPC technique was optimal for all control goals. Another work by Abensur et al. (2020) employed a Nash equilibrium model with competitor-related uncertainty to resolve a home insurance assistance base dispute between two insurers. The mathematical model yielded more realistic location techniques than previous models. In Malaysia, an empirical study by Sanzana et al. (2024) used a serious 3D game to train facility managers and maintainers of thermal energy storage (TES) chiller units in Malaysia. When learning chiller management, employees were more engaged and interested.

In Egypt, Saeed et al. (2023) used game theory and the Shapley value to optimally allocate excess energy to inadequate energy buildings depending on energy demand. Extra electrical power was the payoff. A review of these papers reveals a scarcity of empirical studies on the application of multiple game theory techniques in green building adoption, particularly in Africa. Also, there are limited papers on the application of game theory in the South African context.

Theoretical Framework

In summary, a combination of financial, regulatory, recognition, and other incentives significantly promotes green building practices, contributing to a more sustainable built environment. The theoretical framework for the research aims to provide an understanding of relevant concepts and theories. It focuses on applying game theory strategies and incentives to motivate facility managers to adopt green building practices. Game theory, which examines strategic decision-making among rational individuals, is instrumental in analysing situations where outcomes depend on the decisions of others (von Neumann and Morgenstern, 1944). In the context of green building adoption, understanding the behaviours of facility managers and stakeholders is helpful, as it aids in designing effective incentives for environmentally friendly practices (Li, 2022).

Figure 2: Theoretical framework of the study
Sources: Authors construct (2023)

The World Commission on Environment and Development (1987) defines sustainability as the ability to meet present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Elkington's (1997) Triple Bottom Line model further clarifies this concept by highlighting the interconnectedness of social, environmental, and economic factors. In green buildings, facility managers are crucial in integrating sustainable practices and technologies into building operations.

This research aligns with existing theories and studies by focusing on facilities management objectives, game theory principles, and sustainability practices. Successful realisation of these objectives could aid in implementing game theory to encourage facilities managers to adopt green buildings. By integrating game theory into facility management, we can better understand decision-making processes and strategic interactions among stakeholders. Designing effective incentive mechanisms may help overcome barriers and motivate facilities managers to adopt green building practices, leading to more sustainable built environments.

Methods

Data was collected using online questionnaires given to facilities managers in Johannesburg, South Africa. South Africa, and especially Johannesburg, has the highest number of green buildings on the continent of Africa (City of Johannesburg, 2021) and has an established institution guiding green buildings in other countries of Africa, which is the Green Building Council of South Africa. According to the Green Building Council of South Africa (2025), facilities managers play a crucial role in the context of green buildings. They provide essential information for selecting the right materials and are involved in the operations of green buildings through sustainability initiatives, maintenance, and decommissioning. A non-random convenience sampling technique was employed, as data collection was based on a specific set of conditions (Mukherjee, 2020); namely, the participating population consisted of individuals managing green buildings, which is useful for exploratory studies (Golzar et al., 2022). Questionnaires were sent to 50 respondents, and 33 were returned, representing a 66% response rate. The questions pertained to demographic information, game theory application, and game theory strategies to encourage green practices, which were based on possible strategic decision-making in facilities management for green building adoption that the facilities managers envisaged as possible scenarios between them and other stakeholders. This can be used in analysing situations where outcomes depend on the decisions of others (von Neumann and Morgenstern, 1944). These were presented to the respondents (these are in the text that describes the strategies and incentives/payoffs in figures 1a and 1b in the appendix). The questionnaire also revealed the effectiveness of possible financial and non-financial incentives to promote green practices. The questions were measured using a scale of 1-5. 1= never use, 2=rarely use, 3=sometimes use, 4=often use, 5=always use. 1- Not effective at all, 2= slightly effective, 3= moderately effective, 4= very effective and 5= extremely effective.

Analysis was conducted using SPSS version 20 software. The descriptive analysis was conducted on all the demographic data. Frequency and count analyses were performed on the relevant survey questions, and mean, standard deviation and correlation analyses were used to test for significance between different variables. The analysis employed statistical methods, presenting the findings clearly and concisely. Initially, correlation analysis assessed the strength and direction of relationships between various programs, with correlation values ranging from -1 to 1. A value near 1 indicates a strong positive correlation, a value near -1 indicates a strong negative correlation, and a value near 0 suggests no or a weak correlation. Subsequently, descriptive statistics, such as mean, mode, and standard deviation, were applied to understand the data comprehensively (Adewunmi et al., 2009). Cronbach's alpha was used to test the reliability of the scales, and the scores averaged 0.98, suggesting high reliability of the scales used. Informed consent and ethics clearance were obtained so that the survey would align with the ethics requirements of the School of Construction Economics and Management, University of the Witwatersrand.

Findings

Demographic details of respondents

Regarding education, the most striking observation is the dominance of respondents holding a Bachelor's degree, representing a substantial 63.6% . The next major group comprises those with a Diploma degree at 28%. This suggests that many participants hold at least an undergraduate degree.

The representation of diploma, and honours recipients is relatively minimal, suggesting either a lesser prevalence of these qualifications among the participants or perhaps a more focused target audience for the survey. Regarding work experience, 42% of the participants had up to ten years’ experience and 57% had less experience in green building practices. The designations and roles, including Facilities Manager, Property Manager, Asset Manager, Building Maintenance Manager, Architect, Sustainability Consultant, and Change Manager, had varied representations ranging from 27.3% to 3%. The dominant roles are those of the facilities manager, and the less dominant roles are those of the change manager and asset manager.

Game Theory Strategies

Descriptive Statistics Analysis

Table 1: Game Theory Strategies

Game theory strategies	Mean	SD	Mode	Minimum	Maximum	Sum
Nash Equilibrium	1.96970	0.2197	1	1	5	65
Prisoner’s Dilemma	1.96970	0.2323	1	1	5	65
Zero-sum game	1.7272	0.1756	1	1	5	57
Co-operative Games	2.2121	0.2293	1	1	5	73
Stakelberg model	1.6970	0.1921	1	1	5	56
Repeated Games	2.0909	0.2234	1	1	5	69
Signaling games	1.8788	0.2030	1	1	5	62
Bayesian Games	1.6970	0.1871	1	1	5	56
Evolutionary Game theory	2.0303	0.2282	1	1	5	67

Source: (Authors creation)

An analysis of game theory concepts reveals varying levels of evaluation by the respondents. We can identify the most positively perceived and less favourably regarded concepts by examining the mean values. The analysis showed that managers never or rarely use game theory tools to promote green buildings. The top five concepts with the highest mean values are cooperative games, repeated games, evolutionary game theory, Nash equilibrium, and prisoner’s dilemma. These concepts received mean values ranging from 2.2121 to 1.9697, in order of preference by the respondents. The standard deviations also vary, with values ranging from approximately 1.01 to 1.33, suggesting that the spread of responses is wider for some concepts than others. The mode for all concepts is 1, indicating that this was the most common response. The findings (see Figure 1a in the appendix) imply that the managers prefer green strategies where they can form partnerships, have ongoing relationships, analyse the evolution of green building practices, situations where multiple stakeholders collaborate and where there is a need for the facilities manager to understand the dynamics between tenants and facilities managers regarding shared responsibility (Kalai and Lerer, 1993, Bauso, 2014; Yao and Shao, 2022). The game strategies that were used in other FM studies include Nash equilibrium, repeated games, prisoner’s dilemma, Goodspeed model, savage rule, TU-cost game, and shapely value (Eriksson, 2007; Tamošaitienė et al., 2013; Hopland, 2015; Briata and Fragnelli, 2020; Abensur et al., 2020; Saeed et al., 2023) showing the potential to use evolutionary game theory and other strategies.

Additionally, high positive correlations are observed between certain pairs of game theory concepts. For example, "NASH EQUILIBRIUM" shows a strong positive correlation with "PRISONER'S DILEMMA." These correlations suggest that the other tends to increase as one variable increases.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

	<u>CORRELATION FOR GAME THEORY TOOLS</u>								
	NASH EQ	PRISONO	ZERO-SU	COOPERA	STACKEL	REPEATIS	SIGNALLI	BAYESIA	EVOLUT.
					B	I	NG	N	C
NASH EQ	1								
PRISONO	0.500493	1							
ZERO-SU	0.680779	0.597484	1						
COOPER A	0.492766	0.750602	0.656591	1					
STACKEL B	0.441957	0.672717	0.569251	0.604595	1				
REPEATED	0.676894	0.658504	0.695671	0.709082	0.748057	1			
SIGNAL	0.613201	0.720602	0.794763	0.749711	0.553376	0.7174	1		

LING									
BAYESI AN	0.315534	0.450985	0.497958	0.466219	0.736888	0.700077	0.593079		1
EVOLUT ION	0.567338	0.554501	0.50294	0.629739	0.460274	0.685574	0.738551	0.605656	1

Source: (Authors' creation)

The correlation matrix shows the strength and direction of the relationship between the game theory concepts. For instance, the correlation between Nash Equilibrium and Prisoner's Dilemma is 0.500493, indicating a moderate positive relationship. The correlation between Zero-Sum Games and Signaling Games is 0.794763, indicating a strong positive relationship. Correlation does not imply causation, and other factors could influence these relationships.

Game theory application areas

Table 3: Game Theory Application Areas

Game theory application areas	Mean	SD	Mode	Minimum	Maximum	Sum
Strategic Collaboration	2.6970		1	1	5	89
Resource allocation	3.1212		2	1	5	103
Incentive structuring	2.8489		4	1	5	94
Conflict Resolution	2.3636		1	1	5	78
Cost-Benefit Analysis	3.1818		5	1	5	105
Risk Assessment	2.9394		1	1	5	97
Negotiation strategies	3.1818		4	1	5	105
Regulatory compliance	2.9697		1	1	5	98
Market Dynamics and Competitive Positioning	2.3636		1	1	5	78
Public and Private partnerships	2.1515		1	1	5	71
Supply Chain Optimization	2.0606		1	1	5	68

Financial incentives	Mean	SD	Mode	Minimum	Maximum	Sum
Utility Energy Efficiency Programs	2.3636	0.2568	1	1	5	78
Rebates for Eco-Friendly Materials	2.3939	0.2173	1	1	5	79
Property or Sales Tax Rebates	2.4848	0.2428	1	1	5	82
Sustainable Development Fee Refunds	2.2424	0.2043	1	1	5	74
Permit Fee Discount or Waivers	2.2424	0.2089	1	1	5	74
State Income Tax Credits	2.3333	0.1978	1	1	5	77
Access to Sustainable Project Loan Funds	2.4545	0.2136	1	1	5	81
Federal Grants or Subsidies	2.1515	0.1952	1	1	5	71

Risk Asses	0.553263	0.626714	0.127848	0.027557	0.780767	1											
Negotiatio	0.515082	0.604902	0.033991	0.073779	0.565453	0.595001	1										
Regulator	0.545652	0.614408	0.011392	0.063586	0.817601	0.74783	0.741901	1									
Market Dy	0.340429	0.09156	0.635546	0.719738	0.193891	0.24681	0.053565	0.134213	1								
Public and	0.405814	0.17179	0.568246	0.752341	0.1188	0.318138	0.149279	0.113536	0.740034	1							
Supply Ch	0.233738	-0.04603	0.459187	0.72329	0.087188	0.080405	0.038667	-0.01674	0.650948	0.685787	1						
Energy Eff	0.220796	0.07813	0.584693	0.781037	0.123545	0.214643	0.012937	0.067362	0.802967	0.730946	0.802795	1					
Consumer	0.198619	0.029025	0.58463	0.724889	-0.00313	0.120087	0.017689	-0.04298	0.639211	0.739581	0.717506	0.794937	1				
Benchmar	0.407118	0.187096	0.46499	0.785006	0.188548	0.302312	0.12923	0.178666	0.71701	0.855251	0.754262	0.806221	0.752857	1			
Technolog	0.365522	0.449907	0.316304	0.364009	0.427015	0.444942	0.401991	0.442419	0.47293	0.425774	0.223806	0.49679	0.407285	0.40912	1		

Effectiveness of Financial Incentives in Promoting Sustainable Buildings

Table 5: Financial Incentives

Source: (Authors' creation)

The selected data represents descriptive statistics for various financial incentives that can be used for game theory. The incentives were generally believed to be slightly effective. Among these concepts, the five with the highest mean values are property or sales tax rebates, access to sustainable project loans, rebates for eco-friendly materials, and utility efficiency programs. These concepts received mean values ranging from 2.4848 to 2.3636. On the other hand, the five concepts with the lowest mean values are Federal grants or subsidies, sustainable development fee refunds, permit fee discounts or waivers, and state income tax credits. These concepts received mean values ranging from 2.1515 to 2.3333, suggesting they were less evaluated than others. The mode for all concepts is 1, indicating that this was the most common response for each concept.

Table 6: Correlation Analysis

	Utility Energy Efficiency Programs	Rebates for Eco-Friendly Materials	Property or Sales Tax Rebates	Sustainable Development Fee Refunds	Permit Fee Discounts or Waivers	State Income Tax Credits	Access to Sustainable Project Loan Funds	Federal Grants or Subsidies
Utility Energy Efficiency Programs	1							
Rebates for Eco-Friendly Materials	0.751208	1						
Property or Sales Tax Rebates	0.777418	.748347	1					
Sustainable Development Fee Refunds	0.687667	0.786025	0.74704	1				
Permit Fee Discounts or Waivers	0.760857	0.768771	0.842699	0.645082	1			
State Income Tax Credits	0.652379	0.763491	0.644038	0.687363	0.718111	1		
Access to Sustainable Project Loan Funds	0.613655	0.51182	0.634141	0.420262	0.559627	0.560207	1	
Federal Grants or Subsidies	0.513474	0.737246	0.570969	0.493677	0.784791	0.694713	0.538845	1

Source: (Authors' creation)

A comprehensive correlation analysis has been conducted on various funding and incentive programs associated with energy efficiency and sustainability. This analysis reveals significant relationships between specific pairs of programs. The correlation values, which can range from -1 to 1, suggest the strength and direction of these relationships. For example, the strong positive correlation of 0.751208 between Utility Energy Efficiency Programs and Rebates for Eco-Friendly Materials indicates that an increase in one tends to accompany an increase in the other. Similarly, Property or Sales Tax Rebates and Permit Fee Discounts or Waivers display a strong positive correlation of 0.842699, suggesting that these programs often rise in tandem. Further, a moderate positive correlation exists between Sustainable Development Fee Refunds and Federal Grants or Subsidies and between State Income Tax Credits and Access to Sustainable Project Loan Funds. These correlations, with a value of 0.493677 and 0.560207, respectively, indicate that these programs tend to increase together, although not as consistently as the previous pairs.

Non-Financial incentives	Mean	SD	Mode	Minimum	Maximum	Sum
Technical Assistance	2.5454	0.2136	3	1	5	84
Density Bonus (Higher Floor Area Ratio)	2.3030	0.2063	1	1	5	76
Expedited Permit and Review Process	2	0.1794	1	1	5	66
Free Marketing and Promotion	2.0909	0.2058	1	1	5	69
Recognition Programs	3.0303	0.2556	5	1	5	100
Training and Education Opportunities	3.0303	0.2518	3	1	5	100
Priority or Preferential Zoning	2.1212	0.2076	1	1	5	70
Certifications and Awards	2.8484	0.2467	2	1	5	94

Table 7 : Non-Financial Incentives

Source: (Authors' creation)

The data in Table 7 provides descriptive statistics for non-financial incentives that can be used in game theory. The strategies with the highest mean values, such as recognition programs, training and education opportunities, certifications and awards and technical assistance, with mean scores ranging from 3.0303 to 2.5454. These incentives were perceived to be moderately effective. Other incentives were seen as slightly effective: expedited permit and review process, free marketing and promotion, priority or preferential zoning and density bonus with mean scores ranging from 2 to 2.3030. The mode for all strategies is either 1 or 3, indicating that these were the most common responses for each strategy. However, the range of responses for each strategy extends up to 3 or 4, suggesting significant variability in the data for each strategy.

Findings from previous studies show that the predominant incentive is financial, such as profit and cost, grants and extra energy power (Ericksson, 2007; Briata and Fragnelli, 2020; Saeed et al. (2023). Non-financial incentives could be from learning and mutual cooperation (Ericksson, 2007; Sanzana et al., 2024). Other financial and non-financial incentives studied are in Tables 5 and 7. The findings regarding the incentives are that they are not effective. This could be due to perceived high initial costs, limited knowledge and awareness of green building practices, and a lack of strong regulatory support (Aigbavboa et al., 2017). In the previous section on game theory strategies, we found that cooperative games, repeated games, evolutionary game theory, Nash equilibrium, and prisoner's dilemma were preferred. This implies that when financial incentives such as property or sales tax rebates, access to sustainable project loans, rebates for eco-friendly materials, and utility efficiency programs and non-financial incentives

such as recognition programs, training and education opportunities, certifications and awards and technical assistance are used, they should be a combination of joint rewards, transferable incentives, and long-term, discounted incentives for cooperative and repeated strategies. In the case of the evolutionary and prisoner dilemma, the incentives should be higher, based on productivity, and visually presented. In the Nash equilibrium case, green buildings should not be incentivised (Kalai and Lerer, 1993; Bauso, 2014; Yao and Shao, 2022).

Table 8: Correlation Analysis

	<i>Density Bonus (Higher Floor Area Ratio)</i>	<i>Expedited Permit and Review Process</i>	<i>Free Marketing and Promotion</i>	<i>Recognition Programs</i>	<i>Training and Educational Opportunities</i>	<i>Priority or Preferential Zoning</i>	<i>Certifications and Awards</i>	
Technical Assistance	1							
Density Bonus (Higher Floor Area Ratio)	0.398415	1						
Expedited Permit and Review Process	0.420018	0.716075	1					
Free Marketing and Promotion	0.503283	0.82703	0.61544	1				
Recognition Programs	0.632384	0.138207	0.144554	0.196414	1			
Training and Educational Opportunities	0.624153	0.158478	0.083827	0.345498	0.82354	1		
Priority or Preferential Zoning	0.465907	0.85735	0.788033	0.767659	0.194166	0.215157	1	
Certifications and Awards	0.606218	0.195634	0.192572	0.232344	0.753432	0.703616	0.270112	1

Source: (Authors' creation)

The data represent a correlation matrix for various strategic factors. These correlation values range from -1 to 1. A value close to 1 suggests a strong positive correlation, a value near -1 indicates a strong negative correlation, and a value around 0 shows no or very weak correlation. In this data, Technical Assistance appears to show a strong positive correlation with

Recognition Programs and Training and Educational Opportunities, with values of 0.632384 and 0.624153, respectively; Density Bonus, represented by a higher Floor Area Ratio, exhibits a strong positive correlation with Free Marketing and Promotion and Priority or Preferential Zoning, with correlation values of 0.82703 and 0.85735 respectively. The Expedited Permit and Review Process also strongly correlates with Density Bonus and Priority or Preferential Zoning, with values of 0.716075 and 0.788033, respectively. Additionally, free marketing and promotion have a strong positive correlation with density bonuses, with a correlation value of 0.82703. Furthermore, Recognition Programs and Training and Educational Opportunities exhibit a strong positive correlation of 0.82354. Training and Educational Opportunities also have a strong positive correlation with Certifications and Awards, with a correlation value of 0.703616. Finally, Priority or Preferential Zoning is observed to have a strong positive correlation with the Density Bonus, with a correlation value of 0.85735. These correlations suggest that these strategic factors are often implemented in tandem or may be influenced by similar elements.

Conclusion

The study explored the game-theoretic approach towards the adoption of green building in facilities management in Johannesburg, South Africa. It specifically investigated the adoption of game theory strategies, application areas and game theory incentives towards promoting green buildings by facilities managers. Few empirical studies use a multiple-strategy approach to game theory in facilities management. The study found that cooperative games, repeated games, evolutionary game theory, and Nash equilibrium were preferred game strategies. Cost-benefit analysis, resource allocation, regulatory compliance, incentive structuring, and strategic collaboration were sometimes game theory application areas. Non-financial incentives were rated as better than financial incentives for green building adoption.

Based on the study, it is recommended that expanding and diversifying the data sources is crucial to improve the scope of this research. Along with utilising online surveys, researchers should engage in methods such as conducting interviews and analysing case studies. To mitigate regional biases and improve the relevance of results, researchers should conduct comparative analyses across regions. By thoroughly studying the effectiveness and consequences of game-theoretic tactics and incentive schemes in various areas, researchers can provide more precise guidance tailored to each region's particular needs. Facilities managers' limited knowledge of game theory can be overcome through joint efforts between researchers and educational institutions through advocacy, research and training. Research should focus on prioritising incentive scheme optimisation to improve green building adoption and study the barriers to using game theory strategies. Future research can study the behaviour of facilities management and that of other stakeholders in the built environment. Future research can use random sampling for generalizability of the results and can be conducted in another location or country apart from South Africa.

Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

ORCID

Yewande Adewunmi <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0318-3370>

Prisca Simbanegavi <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7238-3731>

References

Abensur, E.O., da Silva Paes, A., Reyann Kasai Yamada, E., Ruggieri, V. and Alves de Aquino, W., 2020. Stochastic facility location problem in a competitive situation: A game theory model for emergency financial services. *Cogent Engineering*, 7(1), p.1837411.

Adewunmi, Y., Famuyiwa, F. and Harrison, E., 2009. Post-Occupancy Evaluation of Facilities in Nigerian Private Universities: a case study. In *A (Ed) Procs 25th Annual ARCOM Conference, Association of Researchers in Construction Management* (pp. 505-514).

Agbajor, F.D. and Mewomo, M.C., 2024. Green building research in South Africa: A scoping review and future roadmaps. *Energy and Built Environment*, 5(2), pp.316-335.

Aigbavboa, C, Ohiomah, I & Zwane, T 2017. Sustainable construction practices: A “lazy view” of construction professionals in the South African construction industry. *Energy Procedia*, 105: 3003–3010.

Alfalah, G. and Zayed, T., 2020. A review of sustainable facility management research. *Sustainable cities and society*, 55, p.102073.

Wilkinson, N., Ang, R. P., & Goh, D. H. (2008). Online video game therapy for mental health concerns: a review. *International journal of social psychiatry*, 54(4), 370-382.

Armbruster, W. and Böge, W., 1979. Bayesian game theory. In “Game Theory and Related Topics”(Moeschlin, Pallaschke, Eds.).

Bauso, D., 2014. Game theory: Models, numerical methods and applications. *Foundations and Trends® in Systems and Control*, 1(4), pp.379-522.

Bekius, F. and Gomes, S.L., 2023. A framework to design game theory-based interventions for strategic analysis of real-world problems with stakeholders. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 309(2), pp.925-938.

Briata, F. and Fragnelli, V., 2020. Cost Allocation in Common Facilities Sharing. *International Game Theory Review*, 22(01), p.1950010.

Chauhan, N., Rawat, P. and Chauhan, S., 2022. Reinforcement learning-based technique to restore coverage holes with minimal coverage overlap in wireless sensor networks. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, 47(8), pp.10847-10863.

City of Johannesburg (2021). Transitioning towards a Low Carbon Future, Accessed 4th of August, 2025 at [THE CITY OF JOHANNESBURG GREEN BUILDING POLICY: New Buildings](#)

Cohen, C., Pearlmutter, D. and Schwartz, M., 2019. Promoting green building in Israel: A game theory-based analysis. *Building and Environment*, 163, p.106227.

Department of Public Works White Paper Draft 3, DPW GREEN BUILDING POLICY.

Elkington, J., 1997. The triple bottom line. *Environmental management: Readings and cases*, 2, pp.49-66.

Erik Eriksson, P., 2007. Cooperation and partnering in facilities construction—empirical application of prisoner's dilemma. *Facilities*, 25(1/2), pp.7-19.

Fudenberg, D., & Tirole, J. (1991). *Game theory*. MIT Press. Fan, R., Wang, Y., Chen, F., Du, K. and Wang, Y., 2022. How do government policies affect

Gautepllass, A.A. and Hopland, A.O., 2017. Using game theory to stimulate provision of local public facilities. *Property Management*, 35(4), pp.368-379.

Gluch, P., Gustafsson, M., Thuvander, L. and Baumann, H., 2014. Charting corporate greening: environmental management trends in Sweden. *Building Research & Information*, 42(3), pp.318-329.

Golzar, J., Noor, S. and Tajik, O., 2022. Convenience sampling. *International Journal of Education & Language Studies*, 1(2), pp.72-77.

Green Building Council of South Africa (2025), Honouring the Underrated Heroes of Green Buildings: The Critical Role of Facility Managers, Accessed August 8, 2025 at Honouring the Underrated Heroes of Green Buildings | GBCSA

Gundes, S., Yildirim, S.U. (2015) The Use of Incentives in Fostering Green Buildings, *Metu Journal of the Faculty of Architecture*, 32 (2), 45-59.

Hopland, A.O., 2015. Can game theory explain poor maintenance of regional government facilities?. *Facilities*, 33(3/4), pp.195-205.

- Kalai, E. and Lehrer, E., 1993. Rational learning leads to Nash equilibrium. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, pp.1019-1045.
- Kapliński, O. and Tamošaitiene, J., 2010. Game theory applications in construction engineering and management. *Technological and economic development of economy*, 16(2), pp.348-363.
- Krogmann, S., Lenzner, P., Molitor, L. and Skopalik, A., 2021. Two-stage facility location games with strategic clients and facilities. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2105.01425*.
- Li Ang, S. and Wilkinson, S.J., 2008. Is the social agenda driving sustainable property development in Melbourne, Australia?. *Property management*, 26(5), pp.331-343.
- Li, Y., Li, M., Sang, P., Chen, P.H. and Li, C., 2022. Stakeholder studies of green buildings: A literature review. *Journal of building engineering*, 54, p.104667.
- Matisoff, D.C., Noonan, D.S. and Mazzolini, A.M., 2014. Performance or marketing benefits? The case of LEED certification. *Environmental science & technology*, 48(3), pp.2001-2007.
- Mompoti, L., Mandlate, M., Kabini, K. and Nomvalo, U., 2024. Key barriers to green building implementation in South Africa. Proceedings of the WABER SUDBE Conference, 30-31 July 2024, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa
- Myerson, R.B., 2013. *Game theory*. Harvard university press.
- Mukherjee, S., 2020. Disparities, desperation, and divisiveness: Coping with COVID-19 in India. *Psychological Trauma: Theory, Research, Practice, and Policy*, 12(6), p.582.
- Qingfeng, M., Liu, Y., Li, Z. and Wu, C., 2021. Dynamic reward and penalty strategies of green building construction incentive: an evolutionary game theory-based analysis. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(33), pp.44902-44915.
- Saeed, M.A., Eladl, A.A., Alhasnawi, B.N., Motahhir, S., Nayyar, A., Shah, M.A. and Sedhom, B.E., 2023. Energy management system in smart buildings based coalition game theory with fog platform and smart meter infrastructure. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), p.2023.
- Saka, N., Olanipekun, A.O. and Omotayo, T., 2021. Reward and compensation incentives for enhancing green building construction. *Environmental and Sustainability Indicators*, 11, p.100138.

Sanzana, M.R., Abdulrazic, M.O.M., Wong, J.Y. and Yip, C.C., 2024. Personnel training for common facility management issues in thermal-energy-storage chiller plant using a serious 3d game. *Simulation & Gaming*, 55(2), pp.224-248.

Shahmohammadian, A. and Ghafory-Ashtiany, M., 2025. Game theory applications in managing stakeholder conflicts for building safety and resilience against natural disasters. *Progress in Disaster Science*, 26, p.100409.

Simpeh, E.K. and Smallwood, J.J., 2024. Incentive mechanism for promoting the uptake of green building in South Africa. *Open House International*, 49(2), pp.340-357.

Tamošaitienė, J., Peldschus, F. and Al Ghanem, Y., 2013. Assessment of facility management candidates by applying game theory. *Procedia Engineering*, 57, pp.1145-1150.

von Neumann, John and Oskar Morgenstern. (1944). *Theory of Games and Economic Behavior*. Princeton: Princeton University Press. Second edition, 1947; third edition, 1953. Section 3, chapter I, reprinted in Alfred N. Page. (1968). *Utility Theory A Book of Readings*. New York: Wiley, pp. 215- 233.

WCED, S.W.S., 1987. World commission on environment and development. *Our common future*, 17(1), pp.1-91.

Xu, H., Zhai, Z., Wang, K., Ren, S. and Wang, H., 2017. Multiobjective distributed model predictive control method for facility environment control based on cooperative game theory. *Turkish Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Sciences*, 25(5), pp.4160-4171.

Yao, Q. and Shao, L., 2022. Research on decision-making behaviour of stakeholders of low-carbon housing from the perspective of evolutionary game. *Energy Reports*, 8, pp.112-121.